

GINOP-2.1.2-8-1-4-16-2018-00355

Development of a Specialized Twin-Shaft Paddle Feed Mixer Module at Abraziv Kft.'s Kecskemét Site "Support for Corporate R&D&I Activities within the Framework of a Combined Loan Product"

1. Introduction

Technological advancements in animal feed production are crucial for maintaining the competitiveness of the agricultural sector.

Abraziv Kft. is developing a new twin-shaft feed mixer module that enables the post-coating of pelleted feeds with specialized additive components. The fluidized material flow applied in the development process ensures feed integrity, preventing structural damage.

The project is implemented under the Széchenyi 2020 program.

**CONTRACTED GRANT AMOUNT:
HUF 77,936,454**

**PREFERENTIAL LOAN AMOUNT:
HUF 77,936,120**

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2. Technological Foundations of the Development

The twin-shaft paddle mixer is based on Abraziv Kft.'s previous ALK-type single-shaft mixing technology, which has been further optimized in the new system to meet modern feed mixing requirements.

The key features of this innovation include:

- Segmented, precisely measurable mixing process,
- Homogeneous distribution of specialized liquid and solid additive components,
- Modular design allowing for seamless integration into existing feed mixing systems.

3. Market Environment and Demand

Hungary produces approximately 3.5 million tons of feed annually, involving around 20 major production facilities. The expansion potential of this development is significant in the Polish, Romanian, and Balkan markets. Current industry trends, such as the reduction of antibiotic use and the growing demand for precision feeding, further increase the demand for this new mixing technology.

4. Technical Specifications of the Twin-Shaft Feed Mixer Module

- Capacity: 10,000 kg/h (for 3.5 mm diameter pellets)
- Bulk density: 550-650 kg/m³
- Maximum moisture content: 14%
- Processing capability for additives:
 - Animal fat or vegetable oil (max. 500 kg/h)
 - Digestive enzymes
 - Whole wheat grains
- Homogeneity: >1:100000 ratio

5. Innovation Impact and Industrial Application

The development enables the modernization of conventional feed mixing systems without requiring extensive manufacturing modifications. The new technology meets the most advanced feed industry standards while reducing energy consumption and optimizing raw material utilization.

6. Conclusions

The twin-shaft feed mixer module represents a value-adding technological innovation that facilitates the production of higher-quality feeds. With this development, Abraziv Kft. creates opportunities for further expansion in both domestic and international markets while contributing to industrial research and development progress.

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**PLANNED PROJECT
COMPLETION DATE:
December 1, 2020**

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